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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SMART INDONESIA CARD (KIP) PROGRAM IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES (CASE STUDY OF RECIPIENTS WHO DO NOT PURSUE EDUCATION IN BUGIS VILLAGE, TALIWANG DISTRICT, WEST SUMBAWA REGENCY)

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Abstract

The Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program aims to increase access to education for children from underprivileged families in Indonesia. However, in its implementation, there are still KIP recipients who do not continue their education. This study aims to analyze the implementation of the KIP program in Bugis Village, Taliwang District, as well as identify factors that cause beneficiaries not to continue their education. This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. Data was collected through interviews, observations, and documentation from various informants, including KIP recipients who dropped out of school, parents, village officials, and the surrounding community. The results of the study show that several main factors that affect the decision not to continue education include challenges in determining the target recipients, the phenomenon of elopement (merarik), family economic conditions, the influence of a less supportive environment, and low awareness and motivation for education. These findings show that although the KIP program has helped ease the economic burden on families, there are still social and cultural constraints that hinder its effectiveness. Therefore, more adaptive policies and better supervision and socialization are needed to ensure that this program truly contributes to improving the quality of human resources.

Key Words: Smart Indonesia Card, Implementation, Dropout

INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in improving the quality of Human Resources and is one of the pillars of a country's development. The success of an education system is considered good if it is able to produce quality human resources, have the ability, and are committed to improving their quality. This is in accordance with the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution which stipulates that one of the goals of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia is to educate the life of the nation and promote public welfare.

One of the inhibiting factors in education is poverty, because poverty limits people's access to education. Poverty can also reduce people's interest in accessing education, even though education plays an important role in alleviating poverty. Some of the characteristics of the poor can be seen from various aspects, one of which is the economic aspect, where the low quality of human resources including education, health, and skills can have an impact on low incomes, making it difficult to access education.

Improving the quality of education not only has an impact on individuals who receive education but also the socio-economic development of the country as a whole. The Indonesian government realizes the importance of education in developing quality human resources. Therefore, various programs were launched, one of which is the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP). The program is implemented to expand access to education for all levels of society, especially for those from underprivileged families.

The Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program is a program that is a priority by the President of the Republic of Indonesia, Ir. Joko Widodo Number 7 of 2014 and the Regulation of the Minister of Education Number 9 of 2016. This program is a follow-up program of the Poor Student Assistance with the aim of expanding access to education for children aged 6-21 years until they finish their education and prevent dropping out of school. The program was initiated to help students from underprivileged families who are vulnerable to dropping out of school due to economic limitations. Funds for this program are sourced from the Revised State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN-P) and implemented through collaboration between the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Ministry of Social Affairs, and the Ministry of Religion. (Pusea, 2021)

Although the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP) is designed to provide wider access to education and reduce the financial burden of beneficiary families, in practice there are various obstacles that prevent beneficiaries from continuing their education to a higher level. Apart from socioeconomic conditions, lack of family support, students' motivation to continue their education also affects students' decisions to continue their education. This low motivation is usually caused by a lack of awareness of the benefits of education in the long term, both in terms of improving the quality of life and better opportunities in the future. This is what often makes it difficult for KIP recipients to make the most of this program.

Bugis Village is one of the 7 Villages in Taliwang District, West Sumbawa Regency. Bugis Village is one of the areas that has received attention for the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP). As an area with diverse socio-economic backgrounds, and with a relatively stable economy compared to other areas in Taliwang District, it turns out that there is still a

phenomenon of dropping out of school among the recipients of the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP). This is an important question that is relevant to research, because in theory, the KIP program aims to reduce economic barriers in access to education. The selection of Bugis Village is also based on considerations of data accessibility and ease of reaching respondents which allows data collection to be more valid and in-depth.

This study aims to evaluate the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP) in improving the quality of human resources in Bugis Village. This region was chosen because, despite having stable economic conditions, there are still cases of dropping out of school, especially due to social phenomena such as elopement. This research is expected to be able to identify the reasons why KIP recipients do not continue their education and provide recommendations to the government to increase the effectiveness of the program in supporting the improvement of the quality of the workforce in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Implementation

According to Van Meter and Van Horn, implementation is an action taken by individuals, officials, or groups in both the government and private sectors to achieve the goals that have been set in the policy. Implementation is the process of implementing policies into practical actions in order to produce real impacts in the form of changes in knowledge, skills, and values and attitudes (Tasya et al., 2022). In addition, according to (Ulfatimah, 2016), policy implementation is an effort to achieve the goals that have been formulated through various programs by utilizing available facilities and infrastructure and following a predetermined time order.

Program Implementation

Charles O. Jones revealed that policy implementation is an important component of a policy to achieve goals. There are three bases for operating a program, namely: (1) an organization that has flexibility and clear tasks and functions, (2) policy interpretation that is explained to the technical level so that it can be applied immediately, and (3) implementation or application by policy implementers in the field (Abdurrahman, 2022)

According to Korten (1988), the success of a program depends on the alignment of three main elements: the program itself, the implementing organization, and the target group. The program must be in accordance with the needs of the target, the implementing organization must have adequate capacity, and the target group must accept and actively participate in the program.

Smart Indonesia Card (KIP)

The Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) is a form of implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) which aims to increase access to education for children aged 6-21 years from underprivileged families. KIP is a social assistance provided to ease the burden of education costs to prevent school dropouts (Setyawati, 2018). Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 19 of 2016, PIP is an aid fund in the form of cash for students from poor families to support educational costs outside of school operations, such as the purchase of stationery, transportation, pocket money, and additional course fees (Pusea, 2021)

Quality of Human Resources (HR)

The quality of human resources refers to the ability of individuals to carry out their duties and responsibilities effectively with

adequate education, training, and experience support (Suharto Budi, 2021). Human resources are a combination of individual thinking power and physical power that are influenced by hereditary and environmental factors. There are three dimensions of human resource quality according to (Nikmah et al., 2020): (1) knowledge, namely intelligence and mastery of knowledge, (2) skills, namely technical mastery in a certain field, and (3) ability, namely skills that include loyalty, cooperation, and responsibility.

Dropouts

Dropout is a condition in which a student quits school before completing his or her study period. Factors that cause dropping out of school include: (1) limited costs, (2) health conditions, (3) having to work, (4) being paid for by the school, and (5) lack of motivation to continue education (Soetrisnaadisendjaja, 2019). Based on Victor Vroom's Expectancy Theory, motivation to continue education is influenced by three main factors: expectations (the belief that efforts will pay off), instruments (beliefs that assistance such as KIP can reduce economic barriers), and valence (how much a person values education as a path to a better future) (Siagian, 2008)

Socio-Economic Conditions

Socioeconomic conditions describe social and economic situations that include the income status of a person or family in society. This condition plays an important role in determining the quality of education and the development of human resources (HR). In general, socioeconomic conditions include income levels, job stability, and family access to basic needs, including education. Families with higher socioeconomic conditions tend to have greater ability to support children's education, both in terms of costs, learning facilities, and guidance. Conversely, families with weak socioeconomic conditions may have difficulty providing adequate support, which can affect the sustainability of their child's education.

In accordance with the theory of Human Capital put forward by Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz, education is an important investment in improving individual skills, productivity, and economic well-being. Education not only provides basic knowledge but also improves an individual's ability to adapt to economic and social changes. In this context, the KIP Program plays a role in reducing economic barriers for children from underprivileged families. However, the success of this program is also influenced by other factors such as social support, children's motivation, and the environment in which they live (Nurkholis, 2018)

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Approach

This research was conducted using a qualitative method. The qualitative method aims to obtain a complete picture of the problem according to the view of the research subject. Qualitative research refers to the ideas, perceptions, opinions, and beliefs of research subjects, all of which cannot be measured by numbers (Moleong, 2006)

The data collected is in the form of words, pictures, and not numbers. The purpose of using qualitative research is so that researchers can describe the empirical reality behind the events that occurred related to the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program in improving the quality of human resources in Bugis Village. The researcher's consideration of using this study is because the researcher needs more in-depth information related to

the factors that cause recipients of the Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program not to continue their education. So researchers have to face to face and conduct in-depth interviews to get in-depth information as well.

Research Design

According to Abdussamad (2021), research design is very closely related to the research process because research design is a plan to conduct research. This research design can also be interpreted as all the processes involved in the planning and implementation of research. There are several types of qualitative research design, including case studies, descriptive, ethnography, phenomenology, basic theories, and narratives.

In this study, the researcher used a type of case study research. A case study is a series of scientific activities that are carried out intensively and in detail to gain knowledge about a program, event or activity at the level of an individual, group of people, institution, or organization. Usually, the event that is chosen next to be called a case is an actual thing (real-life events) that is taking place, not something that has passed (Rahardjo, 2017).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Description of Informant

The informants from this study amounted to 21 people, namely 12 main informants, of which 7 of them were KIP recipients who dropped out of school and 5 of them were parents of KIP recipients who dropped out of school. There were 8 supporting informants, namely 3 village officials and 5 friends/communities around KIP recipients who dropped out of school. And 1 key informant from the KIP manager at the West Sumbawa Regency Education and Culture Branch Kntor who knows about the implementation of the KIP program in West Sumbawa. For more details, you can see the table below:

Table 4.4 Research Informants

No	Information	Sum	Percentage	Status
1	KIP Manager at the Education and Culture Branch Office, West Sumbawa	1	5%	Key Informant
2	KIP recipients who drop out of school	7	33%	Lead Informant
3	Parents of recipients who drop out of school	5	24%	Lead Informant
4	Village Officials	3	14%	Supporting Informant
5	Community/Friends	5	24%	Supporting Informant
Total		21	100%	3

Research Results

The results of this study will be explained in several points, the first will discuss the Implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP), the second discusses the factors that cause school dropouts consisting of several factors, namely Elopement (Merarik), the Influence of the Community/School Environment, Economic Problems, Lack of Awareness and Motivation.

1. Implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card Program in Bugis Village

The Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) program aims to help children from underprivileged families to continue to go to school. In Bugis Village, this program has been carried out according to government procedures, with KIP recipients determined based on data from the Social Service and verified by the school. Based on an interview with the West Sumbawa Education and Culture Office (KCD), this program has been running well and the majority of beneficiaries come from families in need. However, there are still inaccuracies in the target due to limited data verification, so that some children with economic conditions are better able to receive assistance than those who need it more.

Supervision of the use of funds is also a challenge. Funds that should be used for educational purposes, such as the purchase of school supplies and payment of dues, are sometimes diverted to other needs by recipients. The lack of supervision causes the benefits of this program not always to have a direct impact on improving the quality of education. Overall, the KIP program in Bugis Village has a positive impact on its recipients. However, evaluation of the recipient verification mechanism and supervision of the use of funds are still needed so that this program runs more optimally and on target.

2. Factors Causing School Dropout

Even though the KIP program provides educational assistance, there are still KIP recipients in Bugis Village who choose to drop out of school. Based on the results of the study, there are several main factors that cause school dropout:

3. Kawin Larry (Merarik)

The phenomenon of elopement (Merarik) is one of the main factors in dropping out of school, especially in girls. Based on an interview with the KIP manager at KCD Dikbud West Sumbawa, the main reason for dropping out of school is not economic incapacity, but the child's decision to marry early. Some children choose elopement because of the lack of family support for education, as well as social habits that consider elopement as a way out of personal problems.

4. Influence of Community and School Environment

The surrounding environment plays a very important role in students' decisions to continue their education. Some students drop out of school due to negative peer influences, such as promiscuity and drunken habits. In addition, some students were expelled from school for violating disciplinary rules, as well as experiencing bullying, which made them lose their enthusiasm for learning.

5. Economic Problems

Despite KIP's provision of education cost assistance, some families still experience economic hardship that encourages their children to work rather than continue schooling. This economic factor is not only related to school fees, but also daily living needs. Some children choose to drop out of school to help their parents make ends meet, especially if one parent has died or is chronically ill.

6. Lack of Awareness and Motivation

Lack of awareness of the importance of education is another factor that causes school dropouts. Some students feel bored with school routines and lose interest in learning. The lack of variety in learning methods and lack of support from family are also the causes of their low motivation to continue their education.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Card Program (KIP) in Bugis Village, Taliwang District, West Sumbawa Regency, it was found that this program has not been fully effective in preventing school dropout rates. The program has been running well and the majority of beneficiaries come from families in need. However, there are still inaccuracies in the target due to limited data verification, so that some children with economic conditions are better at receiving assistance than those who need more, the phenomenon of elopement (merarik), the influence of the community and school environment, economic problems, and lack of awareness and motivation from the students themselves.

The KIP program still faces obstacles in terms of recipient verification, supervision of the use of funds, and a lack of public understanding of the program's objectives. In addition, cultural factors such as elopement and juvenile delinquency in the school and community environment further aggravate the condition. Economic factors and lack of encouragement from the family also contribute to the child's decision not to continue his education.

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